

SECTION II

LANGUAGE PEDAGOGY IN A GLOBAL CONTEXT: ENHANCING LEARNING AND COMMUNICATION

MEANS OF DEVELOPING REFLECTION OF PROFESSIONAL PERSONAL QUALITIES OF A YOUNG TEACHER

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Abstract:

The author reflects on the phenomenon of reflection as well as professional reflection; and their main importance in the teaching sphere, especially, for the beginner teacher. Furthermore, in the article it is possible to find some advice on some skills and abilities that a young teacher should possess. Additionally, the author provides data on the observation diary, which is accumulated by reflexive skills that will develop the habit of self-education plan.

Key words: professional development, modern educational paradigm, pedagogical reflection, self-creation, self-realization, self-education, professional competence

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The professional development of a teacher is a continuous process of improving professionally significant qualities under the influence of social influences, pedagogical activity and the individual's own activity. In accordance with the modern educational paradigm, the teacher must constantly monitor and adjust their personal growth, reflect on the results of their professional activities.

Let us note that professional reflection is the correlation of oneself, the capabilities of one's "I" with what the chosen profession requires; including – with existing ideas about it. It helps a person to note achievements and failures in performance results, see problems and solve them at the expense of their internal resources, make their own choices, take responsibility for their decisions. Reflexive mechanisms make it is possible for a person to perceive a new positive experience and its creative rethinking, help to formulate the results obtained, predetermine the goals of further work, adjust one's professional path.

G.G. Ernst notes that thanks to professional reflection, professional competence increases, expressed in the volume of specific knowledge and skills in the field of one's profession, the development of skills in posing and solving problems, the ability of collective interaction and overcoming conflict situations, enriching professional and personal experience. This allows a person to form his

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own values and principles, determine a strategy for one's own development, encourages self-development and a creative attitude towards professional activities [2, p. 25].

Pedagogical reflection is understood as professional reflection, but in content related to the characteristics of teaching work and one's own experience. When it is implemented, a process of self-creation of a teacher as a subject of pedagogical activity through the correlation of his opportunities occurs, individual experience, competence with the requirements of professional activity. A young specialist needs to know what skills and abilities he should have, to understand to what extent he has developed these skills and abilities for successful self-realization in pedagogical activities.

Reflection, in our opinion, contributes to the development of three very important qualities of a young specialist necessary for work in the third millennium:

- independence – the ability to analyze, realize one's capabilities, make one's own choices, determine the level of activity and responsibility in one's activities;
- entrepreneurship - the ability to realize what he can do here and now, so that it gets better, and in case of an error or failure, evaluate situation and, based on new conditions, set new goals and objectives and successfully solve them;
- competitiveness – the ability to do something better than others, to act most effectively in any situation.

Teacher reflection is one of the indicators of professional competence, characterizes his ability to self-educate, strive for growth, and self-improvement. Based on the above, the task of developing reflexive competence of a young teacher, which must be solved from the very first steps in the formation of professional qualities, since in relation to all other qualities, reflexivity acts as a coordinating, organizing and integrating principle.

To do this, it is necessary to create conditions that ensure the development of personal and professional reflection of young specialists, interested attitude towards reflexive activity, stimulating the actual reflexive behavior of the professional as a whole.

These conditions may include such activities as: inclusion of young teachers in special forms of advanced training, providing the opportunity to develop professional competence through innovative technologies; reflective practices, game modeling of various situations; supervision, which allows you to evaluate yourself as a specialist and form your professional identity; group discussions, helping to compare opposing positions, to see the problem from different sides, etc.

This includes the creation of a specially organized environment in which co-creation is stimulated, conditions for choice are created and relations between participants in reflective activity. It is necessary that every young teacher makes reflection a daily need, since the learning process is extremely intensive in everyday events for the individual, if these events are used as a tool for professional and personal growth.

Since pedagogical reflection stimulates research, creative process, leads the teacher to new tasks of conscious professional activity, this allows him to realize his difficulties, find ways to overcome them. In addition, the activity of the youngest teacher is no less important in the development of reflection. With the help of questionnaires and maps of individual difficulties, a novice teacher can analyze the nature of his difficulties and mistakes [1, p. 98].

It is very important for a young teacher to be able to evaluate his own professionally significant skills. For this purpose, you can use a modified version of the method of self-assessment of the level of professional development. nationally significant skills of a teacher [3, p. 112].

Significant assistance in mastering reflexive skills can be provided by an individual pedagogical observation diary, in which the results of one's own observations and the dynamics of professional development are entered in free form. Along with diaries, it is important for a young teacher to form an individual self-education plan in areas of professional development significant qualities, development of individual character traits.

All of the above methods collected in this article will allow a young teacher to accumulate experience in experiencing and overcoming professional difficulties, become a professional and reach the level creative activity, which is the highest level, the end point of professionalism.

Literature:

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